

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF THE HUMIC PREPARATION "ROSTOK" ON THE GERMINATION OF VEGETABLE SEEDS IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

This article presents the results of a study on the effectiveness of processing vegetable seeds with a humic preparation. In the region of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the influence of the humic preparation "Rostok" on the germination and productivity of vegetable crops was studied.

Seed treatment with a humic preparation "Rostok" involves the improvement of production technologies not only in terms of quantitative and qualitative improvement, but also in terms of maintaining environmental safety and balance of agro ecosystems.

Presowing seed treatment with a humic preparation "Rostok" contributed to an increase in the field germination of seeds of the "Rubin" radish - by 15% and increased the yield by 1.3 kg / m².

Presowing treatment with a humic preparation "Rostok" allows to increase the germination energy of vegetable seeds, allows unconditioned seeds to be brought to sowing conditions in terms of germination, which makes it possible to save seed material, increase the yield of vegetable crops.

Keywords: humin, preparation, yield, vegetable, germination, control, growth.

Introduction: The modern scientific system of agriculture involves the transition to greening and biologization, aimed at producing environmentally friendly products with minimal use of chemicals [1].

Ensuring food security of the Republic of Kazakhstan is a priority task. Vegetable crops are of great importance among the plant growing products. Carrot, radish and beet varieties are among the most responsive crops to mineral nutrition and the use of growth stimulants.

The difficult economic conditions prevailing at the present time set the task of vegetable producers to obtain high, stable yields and high quality products using resource-saving and economical technologies. This problem can be solved by directly managing the growth and development of plants using new agricultural techniques. A modern direction is the search and development of such techniques that could increase the yield of crops with minimal use of chemicals. One of these areas is the use of humic preparations produced on the basis of natural organic sources, incl. peat. Due to the structural features and physicochemical properties, they are characterized by high physiological activity, activate the metabolism of beneficial micro flora, increase the defense mechanism of plants against the action of unfavorable climatic factors, and contribute to the formation of a high yield of vegetable crops. The studies of the authors (V.S. Vinogradov, Yu.V.

Smirnov) revealed a positive ecological effect of treatments with humic stimulants on vegetable crops [2].

Seed treatment with a humic preparation "Rostok" involves the improvement of production technologies not only in terms of quantitative and qualitative improvement, but also in terms of maintaining environmental safety and equilibrium of agroecosystems [3]. In modern technologies for the cultivation of vegetable crops, great importance is attached to the methods of pre-sowing seed treatment with new environmentally friendly preparations that improve the sowing quality of seeds, stimulate the growth and development of plants, increase productivity, as well as foliar dressing, which increase both the yield and the quality of products [4].

According to a number of researchers, the use of plant growth regulators (PPP) is one of the most promising ways to increase plant productivity. Their effectiveness is largely determined by the potential capabilities of the plants themselves, as well as the growing conditions [5].

Both natural and synthetic compounds can be used as exogenous plant growth regulators. Their use makes it possible to enhance or weaken the signs and properties of plants within the normal range set by the genotype, to increase the resistance of plants to adverse conditions, to compensate for the shortcomings of varieties and hybrids. Due to their high efficiency in small doses,

these drugs usually meet the current increasingly stringent requirements for environmental safety [6].

The use of growth stimulants provides an increase in the yield and quality of grown products, an increase in resistance to diseases and other stressful influences, an improvement in fruit set, an acceleration of ripening, a decrease in the content of nitrates, radionuclides, etc. Plant growth regulators are classified from various positions: by chemical composition, crops, influence on the physiological processes of plants, etc. [7].

The goal is to develop a technology for the use of a humic preparation "Rostok" for obtaining environmentally friendly vegetable products. Presowing treatment with a humic preparation "Rostok" allows to increase the germination energy of vegetable seeds, allows unconditioned seeds to be brought to sowing conditions in terms of germination, which makes it possible to save seed material, increase the yield of vegetable crops.

Research method: The high efficiency of the use of humic preparations has been proven many times. To develop a technology for the use of a humic preparation "Rostok" for obtaining ecologically safe vegetable products.

The influence of the method of extraction, composition and concentration of the reagent, stages of purification from impurities on the chemical composition of humic preparations from peat was studied.

On the basis of technological experience and the results of field tests, since 2001, the research and production center "Eureka", created as part of the department, began to carry out experimental production of a modified highly purified humic preparation "Rostok". It is obtained by chemical modification of humic acids extracted from peat. As a result of changes in the structure and properties of humic acids, their biological activity and ability to penetrate through cell membranes increase [8].

The preparation contains complex compounds of humic acids. It is recommended for use in agriculture, communal, forestry and personal subsidiary plots in the

form of aqueous solutions for treating seeds (tubers, bulbs, seedlings, cuttings, etc.) and plants of all types of crops at various phenological stages of development in 2-4 terms after 10 -15 days. The drug can be used in the form of pre-sowing treatment (0.5 l / t 1% of the drug, solution consumption 10 l / t) and foliar treatment (100 ml of 1% drug per 100 l of solution, solution consumption 200-400 l / ha; with low volume spraying with 200 ml / ha of 1% preparation).

The drug has a significant effect on the redox processes in the plant cell, activates protein synthesis and carbohydrate metabolism, has stimulating and anti-stress properties. The energy of seed germination, root formation, growth and development of the aerial part, product quality, plant resistance to diseases increase, and the passage of phenological phases is accelerated [9].

Germination (laboratory and field) - the ability of seeds to form normally developed seedlings. Field germination is lower than laboratory germination, since it is impossible to create optimal conditions in the field, as in the laboratory.

It is possible to increase the germination energy and germination capacity by pre-sowing treatment with the Rostock preparation (0.5 l / t), adding it to the dressing agent. In addition, plants develop a more powerful root system.

According to the results of our research, the humic preparation "Rostok" increased the germination energy of vegetable seeds (table 1). So the germination of seeds treated with a humic preparation on table beets of the "Bordeaux 237" variety and the radish of the "Rubin" variety was one hundred percent. Germination of seeds of carrot varieties "Nantskaya" was very high 93%, while in the control the level of germination of carrot seeds was 71%.

Figure 1 shows that the use of the humic preparation "Rostok" made it possible to improve the germination of beet seeds and provided a 16% increase to the control.

Figure 1. Germination of seeds of Beetroot "Bordeaux 237" treated with SE "Rostok" and increase to control%.

The positive effect of the treatment of carrot seeds with the humic preparation "Rostok" is evidenced by the excellent result of field germination of 93%. Which exceeded the control option by 22%, the data is shown in

Figure 2. Germination of seeds of "Rubin" radish treated with SE "Rostok" and % increase to control.

Our observations are confirmed by long-term field and production tests of the humic preparation "Rostok" on vegetable crops. I would like to note that, at present, it is used in the farms of many regions of Russia and Kazakhstan.

The sprout helps to increase the field germination of seeds, the energy of germination, and affects the growth and development of vegetable crops. Experiments on vegetable crops confirm the studies of the effect of the humic preparation "Rostok" on the germination energy of spring wheat, barley and oil flax, when using which the germination energy increased by 23.5%, 37.1%, 8.2%, respectively. In studies of the use of the humic preparation "Rostok" in a tank mixture with herbicides, it was possible to increase the field germination of wheat - 81.2%, barley - 78.8%, and flax - 91.2.

The drug activates metabolic processes, resulting in an increased consumption of minerals from the soil. Seedlings on the plots did not appear all at once, they are stretched to one degree or another. This can be explained by the fact that not only the pre-sowing treatment but also the quality of the seeds, the conditions of moistening the upper layer of the soil, its temperature, the uniformity of the depth of seeding, the quality of soil preparation and other factors affect the amicability of the seedlings.

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